

p-DIALKYLAMINOSTYRYL DYES DERIVED FROM 5-ARYLAMINOTHIADIAZOLES

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By condensation of the following pairs: (1) 5-phenylamino-2-methylthiadiazole and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, (2) 5-phenylamino-2-methylthiadiazole and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde methiodide, (3) 5-phenylamino-2,3-dimethylthiadiazolium iodide and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, three compounds (one colorless, one yellow and the third, red) have been obtained and their colours explained in terms of resonance theory. Six 5-arylamino-2,3-dimethyl-1:3:4-thiadiazolium iodides have also been prepared and condensed with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde to yield the corresponding *p*-dialkylaminostyryl dyes. Their absorption spectra have been measured and their deviations calculated and compared with the deviations obtained in case of *p*-dialkylaminostyryl dyes derived from quinoline, benzothiazole and thiazoles. Since deviations are a measure of basicity, the greater deviation of dyes derived from thiadiazoles indicates that it is more basic than benzothiazole or quinoline. The sensitisation spectra of dialkylaminostyryl dyes have also been measured.

2-*p*-Dimethylaminostyryl-5-phenylamino-1:3:4-thiadiazole(I), formed by the condensation of 5-phenylamino-2-methyl-1:3:4-thiadiazole with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, gives rise to two mono-methiodides, one a red compound and the other, almost colorless (separated by fractional crystallisation). The red compound is identical with the product formed by condensation of 5-phenylamino-2,3-dimethyl-1:3:4-thiadiazolium iodide with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, and the colorless compound could also be similarly obtained by condensing the methiodide of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde with 5-phenylamino-2-methyl-1:3:4-thiadiazole. The existence of resonance and the long conjugated chain contribute to the deep colour in the red compound. The yellow colour of the base (I) is due to the fact that degeneracy of the system, neutral $\rightarrow$ charged structure, is very low.

In the present investigation, several 5-arylamino-2-methyl-1:3:4-thiadiazoles have been prepared. Their corresponding thiadiazolium iodides have been condensed with *p*-dimethylamino- and *p*-diethylamino-benzaldehydes to give rise to the corresponding *p*-dialkylaminostyryl dyes. The absorption spectra of the dyes have been measured in the visible spectrophotometer (Upicam S.P. 600).

In order to estimate the basicity of the thiadiazole nucleus, relative to benzothiazole and quinoline etc., the deviation observed in *p*-dialkylaminostyryl dye (I) has been compared with that shown by the corresponding dyes derived from benzothiazole, quinoline and thiazole. It is known that the greater the deviation shown by a styryl dye, the greater is the basicity of the nitrogen heterocyclic ring involved. The deviation has been calculated by regarding the dye (I)

as the structural cross between the symmetrical dye (II) and the acidified form of Michler's hydrol (III). Calculating in this manner, the deviations of the dyes derived from thiaziazole, quinoline and benzothiazole compounds have been found to be 85, 80, 45 $m\mu$ respectively, thus showing that 5-phenylaminothiaziazole nucleus is more basic than either quinoline or benzothiazole.

In order to examine the absorption spectra of styryl-cyanine system in which the resonance interaction of *N*-dimethylamino group is absent, 5-phenylamino-2:3-dimethylthiaziazolium odide has been condensed with furfuraldehyde and thiophene-2-aldehyde. The colour of this system may be attributed to resonance between the structures (IVa) and (IV b). These compounds absorb at much shorter wave-lengths, thus indicating a sufficiently high energetic asymmetry between the two extreme structures.

The sensitisation spectra of some of the compounds have also been measured by the method of Doja *et al.* (this *Journal*, 1941, 18, 281) with slight modifications.

The light source was a 100 watt tungsten lamp instead of a 100 C.P. (point-o-lite) lamp. An wedge was placed in front of the slit to serve the purpose of rotating logarithmic sector used by Doja and co-workers. An internal scale was used to read the wave-length.

EXPERIMENTAL

5-p-Tolylamino-2:3-dimethyl-1:3:4-thiadiazolium Iodide.—The base, 5-*p*-tolylamino-2-methyl-1:3:4-thiadiazole, was prepared by the action of acetyl chloride (6-7 c.c.) on ice-cooled *p*-tolylthiosemicarbazide (3 g.), the latter being obtained by reacting an ice-cooled 50% solution of hydrazine hydrate with an ice-cooled ethanolic solution of *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate. On completion of the reaction the excess of acetyl chloride was removed and the syrupy mass was treated with ammonia to yield the base. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 194°, yield 78%.

The corresponding iodide was prepared by heating the above base (1 *M*) with methyl iodide (1.2 *M*) in a sealed tube for 48 hours at 100°. The solid, isolated from the reaction mixture, was

washed with ether and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 182°, yield 90%. (Found: I, 36.5. $C_{11}H_{13}N_3IS$ requires I, 36.7%).

The properties and analytical data etc. of other thiadiazoles and their corresponding methiodides are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Nature of R.	M. P. of the base.	Methiodides.		% Iodine.	
		Yield.	M.P.	Found.	Calc.
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	203°	73%	198°	36.60	36.70
Phenyl	191°	80	163°	36.20	36.25
<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	178°	72	203°	32.78	32.70
<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	167°	82	186°	34.90	34.98
<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	234°	80	162°	30.71	30.82

5-p-Tolylamino-2-p-dimethylaminostyryl-3-methylthiadiazolium Iodide.—To a mixture of *5-p*-dimethylamino-2,3-dimethyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolium iodide (0.32 g.) and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.15 g.), dissolved in absolute ethanol (10 c.c.), piperidine (2 drops) was added and the mixture refluxed for 4 hours. It was chilled; the fine needle-shaped crystals separating were washed with ether and finally crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 182°, yield 58%. (Found: C, 49.9; H, 4.88. $C_{20}H_{23}N_4IS$ requires C, 50.1; H, 4.8%). It shows absorption maximum at 480 $m\mu$.

The properties and analytical data of other compounds of this series are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	R ₁ .	R ₂ .	λ_{max} .	M.P.	Yield.	% Carbon.		% H, nitrogen.	
						Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Et	491 $m\mu$	228°	47%	52.10	52.07	5.35	5.52
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	Me	480	118°	38	49.78	50.10	4.90	5.01
3.	..	Et	490	130°	33	52.00	52.07	5.38	5.52
4.	Phenyl	Me	..	222°	47	49.20	49.03	4.58	4.50
5.	..	Et	..	207°	35	51.30	51.10	4.98	5.20
6.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	Me	..	240°	30	49.52	49.60	4.70	4.90
7.	..	Et	..	216°	38	51.62	51.70	5.31	5.40
8.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Me	..	240°	36	48.81	48.90	4.50	4.64
9.	..	Et	..	216°	43	..	..	..	..
10.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	Me	..	262°	42	41.94	41.90	3.58	3.70
11.	..	Et	..	218°	40	..	..	..	..

6-Methyl-2-p-dimethylaminostyryl-1-ethylquinolinium Iodide.—A mixture of 2:6-dimethylquinoline ethiodide (0.31 g.) and p-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.14 g.), dissolved in ethanol (10 c.c.), was refluxed for 2 hours after addition of piperidine (2 drops). On cooling, the solid separating was collected and crystallised from ethanol as deep red needles, m.p. 254°, yield 62%.

Similarly were prepared the following: 6-Methyl-2-p-diethylaminostyryl-1-ethylquinolinium iodide, 4-p-bromophenyl-2-p-dimethylaminostyryl-3-methylthiazolium iodide and 4-p-bromophenyl-2-p-diethylaminostyryl-3-methylthiazolium iodide.

2-p-Dimethylaminostyryl-5-phenylamino-1:3:4-thiadiazole.—A mixture of 5-phenylamino-2-methyl-1:3:4-thiadiazole (3 g.) and p-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (1.14 g.), dissolved in ethanol (20 c.c.), and piperidine (2 drops) was refluxed in a steam-bath for 6 hours. Excess of alcohol was removed and on cooling, a solid separated out which was collected and crystallised from ethanol as colorless cubes, m.p. 172°, yield 70%. (Found: S, 9.85. $C_{18}H_{18}N_4S$ requires S, 9.9%).

The methiodide of the above compound was prepared by heating the thiadiazole (3.2 g.) and MeI (1.8 g.) in a sealed tube for 24 hours. The product obtained after washing with ether was deep red in colour. It was crystallised. The first fraction which crystallised out was red in colour and had m.p. 220° and found to be identical with compound No. 4 of Table II.

The second fraction which crystallised out was almost colorless and had m.p. 191°. (Found: C, 49.3; H, 4.6. $C_{18}H_{21}N_4IS$ requires C, 49.03; H, 4.5%).

5-Phenylamino-3-methyl-2-(2-thenylvinyl)-1:3:4-thiadiazolium Iodide.—A mixture of 5-phenylamino-2:3-dimethyl-1:3:4-thiadiazolium iodide (3 g.) and thiophene-2-aldehyde (1 g.), dissolved in absolute ethanol (10 c.c.), and piperidine (2 drops) was refluxed for 2 hours. It was cooled and the excess of alcohol removed under reduced pressure. The resulting gum was washed several times with ether. On crystallisation from ethanol yellow plates were obtained, m.p. 244°, yield 40%. It shows absorption maximum at 415 m μ .

5-Phenylamino-3-methyl-2-(2-furylvinyl)-1:3:4-thiadiazolium Iodide.—5-Phenylamino-2:3-dimethyl-1:3:4-thiadiazolium iodide (3 g.) and furane-2-aldehyde (12 g.) were used for the preparation of this compound. It was isolated in the same manner as above, when the product was obtained as brown crystals, m.p. 238° (decomp.), yield 52%. It shows absorption maximum at 422 m μ .

Sensitisation.—The sensitisation spectra of four compounds, namely, compounds No. 4, 5, 10 and 11 of Table II are given. Refer to photographs, B-1 (Comp. No. 4), B-2 (Comp. No. 5), B-3 (Comp. No. 10), B-4 (Comp. No. 11) and the photograph without any mark is that of the unsensitised plate.

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